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Abstract

In August 2000, 189 United Nations member nations opined on "Globalization and Its Impact on the Full Enjoyment of Human Rights" in light of several staggering issues confronting the world, including the world population of 6 billion, ozone layer depletion, rapid climate change, malnutrition, AIDS, peace, security, and disarmament, human rights, development, and poverty eradication. Globalization as it currently exists tends to enrich the "haves" while further marginalising the "have-nots." All of the aforementioned difficulties are the impetus for the establishment of Voluntary Agencies such as Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), which are formed by members of society for the purpose of improving society in some way. Despite their accomplishments in a variety of disciplines, NGOs face a variety of challenges that vary by organisation and region. In this context, the purpose of this paper is to address some of the most prevalent challenges encountered by NGOs and to suggest some solutions for resolving them.

Keywords: Non-Government Organization, MDG, Partnership and collaboration.

The Road Ahead to Achieve Millennium Development Goals through NGOs

Introduction

In September 2000, 189 countries signed the United Nations Millennium Declaration, committing themselves to eradicating extreme poverty in all its forms by 2015. To help track progress toward these commitments, a set of time-bound and quantified goals and targets, called the Millennium Development Goals, were developed for combating poverty in its many dimensions — including reducing income poverty, hunger, disease, environmental degradation and gender discrimination.

The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) include 8 goals, 21 targets and 60 indicators for measuring progress between 1990 and 2015, when the goals are expected to be met. The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) are eighth international development goals that were established with some objectives like to eradicate extreme poverty and hunger, to achieve universal primary education, to promote gender equality and empowering women, to reduce child mortality rates, to improve maternal health, to combat HIV/AIDS, malaria, and other diseases, to ensure environmental sustainability and to develop a global partnership for development.

As of 2013 progress towards the goals was uneven. Some countries achieved many goals, while others were not on track. Among the non-governmental organizations assisting were the Millennium Campaign, the Millennium Promise Alliance, Inc., the Global Poverty Project etc. to make it successful till 2015.

The MDGs arguably represent the greatest opportunity and challenge for alleviating poverty and improving quality of life globally in our time. Their achievement will require maximizing all available

resources and capitalizing on all available actors. NGOs have been highlighted by governments and global leaders as an important actor, but without better understanding of their potential, roles, and challenges to their effectiveness, we are not likely to fully tap their contribution and thus will be further challenged in achieving the MDGs.

"A well-thought out and ambitious attempt to place the roles of NGOs within the multi-faceted and often muddled challenge of achieving Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). The NGOs in our contemporary, globalized society makes clear what roles they are playing now and can do more of in our collective call against poverty."

Objectives

- To analyze the role of NGOs in promoting development in India,
- To understand the limitations in the functions of NGOs

Global application of Millennium Development Goals

“Globalization and continuing rapid technological advances offer unprecedented opportunities for social and economic development. At the same time, they continue to present serious challenges, including widespread financial crises, insecurity, poverty, exclusion and inequality within and among societies. Considerable obstacles to further integration and full participation in the global economy remain for developing countries....Unless the benefits of social and economic development are extended to all countries, a growing number of people in all countries and even entire regions will remain marginalized from the global economy.”

Consequently, the UN laid down the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in the year 2000 and set the year 2015 as the deadline for achieving them. The MDGs were also meant to act as a wide framework for the entire international community to work together towards a common end – making sure that human development reaches everyone, no matter to which nationality he/she belongs to. Some of the actors in the Millennium Development Initiative include such as Governments, Bilateral agencies (e.g. SIDA, USAID, DFID, DANIDA, JICA) and Multilateral Agencies (WTO, OECD) and Civil Society organisations (in their multitude) and Trade Unions. To date, documenting progress on MDGs has not been easy from a global point of view. What come out are country specifics about some sectors of the development goals. Progress in countries' income such as China and India has been registered. There is also commitment of resources by the corporate e.g. Bill and Melinda Gates to a tune of US \$ 4.9 Billion in Global Health programmes. Countries such as Uganda have made significant progress in the area of universal primary education.

Some of the challenges that have beset the MDGs to date include: decline in average income of some countries; lack of knowledge on MDGs by one-third of respondents in 75 countries (World Federation of UN Associations); government suspicion of CBOs on the level of their commitment to the people they serve. DFID Report (2006) notes that unfortunately, while some significant progress is being made towards meeting some of the targets in some of the affected countries, in many cases progress is patchy, too slow or non-existent. Although improvements have been made in many areas in Sub-Saharan Africa, for example, the number of people living in poverty there is still greater now than it was in 1990.

The rest of the developing world has outstripped Africa in most if not all areas. The World Bank report (2004) notes the following challenges: Regional trends show the greatest progress in East Asia and the Pacific, but malnutrition rates remain high in South Asia and are rising in Sub-Saharan Africa. Three regions –East Asia and the Pacific, Europe and Central Asia, and Latin America and the Caribbean – are on track to achieve the goal. But the other three regions, the Middle East and North Africa, South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa, which have 150 million children of primary school age, are in danger of falling short. Sub-Saharan Africa lags farthest behind, with little progress since 1990.

South Asia also has chronically low enrolment and completion rates eliminating gender disparities in primary and secondary education by 2005- and at all levels of education by 2015. Progress has been particularly slow in Sub-Saharan Africa, where civil disturbances and HIV/AIDS have driven up rates of infant and child mortality in many countries. But in Africa, where skilled attendants and health facilities are not readily available, it is very high. The MDG Progress Report (2005) sub Saharan Africa is lagging behind on many of the goals and targets. Maternal mortality outcomes are difficult to measure, and the lack of reliable data across countries and over time limits the ability to track progress towards this goal. But current trends suggest that the goal will almost certainly not be met. According to UNAIDS (2006) Report today, an estimated 38.6 million people world-wide are currently infected with HIV, with roughly 4.1 million new cases reported in 2005.

Most African countries have taken on the MDGs as conduits to addressing extreme poverty within their populations, although the performance is varying depending on the specific goals they are trying to address. This is a significantly positive shift in Africa's quest for development with 90% of its population enmeshed into deprivation trap². Some Goals such as Universal Primary Education, as with Uganda have been undertaken with remarkable resilience.

NGOs in India

NGOs or Voluntary Organizations are not a new phenomenon and the concept of voluntary action is very ancient. According to Inamdar, "During ancient and medieval times, voluntarism operated freely and exclusively in the fields of education, medicine, cultural promotion and even acted as succour in crises like droughts, floods, epidemics and foreign invasions" (1987).

In the early years of 19th century, voluntary agencies provided services to the under-privileged and weaker sections of the society. The areas of operation were largely in the fields of religion and social reforms. Raja Rammohan Roy (1772 -1833), Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar (1820-1891), Sasi Pada Banarjee (1842-1925), Keshab Chandra Sen (1838-1884), Swami Dayanand Saraswati (1824-1883), Swami Vivekanand (1863- 1902), Mahatma phule (1827-1888), Pandit Ramabai (1858-1922), Maharshi Karve (1858-1962), Sir Sayyed Ahmed Khan (1817-1898), Behramji Malbari (1853-1912) were the people who worked with dedication towards removal of caste restrictions, improving conditions of widows, women education, orphans and destitute women etc,. In the latter part of 19th century, Christian Missioners also did pioneering work in the field of social welfare. They also took interest in spreading education among women, tribal, and others, and in improving their health and living conditions.

In the early decades of 20th century besides relief and rehabilitation programmes in times of natural calamities like earth quakes, floods and famines, NGOs were also engaged in various fields like education, health and labour welfare. According to Chowdhry, "After Independence, leadership in India

was provided by social workers who had worked under the leadership of Gandhi. As a matter of fact, they were the ones who started the movement of voluntary action, both in urban and rural areas in the fields of health, education, social welfare, adult education, rural development etc.,” (1987). The government undertook welfare schemes under various plans and policies, besides encouraging voluntary organizations to undertake social welfare programmes under the grant-in-aid programme and set up autonomous bodies like Central Social Welfare Board, Indian Council of Social Welfare etc.,

Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) have become an irresistible global force today. The non-governmental sector, also known as voluntary sector, is growing in relation to its presence in developmental activities. Its role in the sphere of human development is now widely recognized and accepted in most parts of the universe. Basically, an NGO or voluntary organisations are non-profit making agencies that are constituted with a vision by a group of like-minded people, committed for Non-governmental organisations are playing an increasingly decisive role in shaping the economy and facilitating inclusive growth at the grassroots level in a large, multi-ethnic and highly populated country like India, where it is not always possible for the government to ensure that its development schemes and policies reach the backwaters of society.

NGOs in India attempts to highlight the activities of these organisations in the region and educate people on the role played by these in facilitating inclusive growth, thus ensuring development in every strata of society.

Role of Non-government Organisations (NGOs) in the development process in the third world countries like India is very crucial, especially in the 21st Century. They have a greater role to play in the lives and livelihoods of the tribal and backward communities of India today. An attempt has been made in this paper to see the role of an NGO in the development of a country. It is also attempted to understand how the information and support from the agency (NGO) helped the community to become self-reliant.

As development actors, NGOs have become the main service providers in countries where the government is unable to fulfill its traditional role. Optimal development requires the harnessing of a country's assets, its capital, human and natural resources to meet demand from its population as comprehensively as possible. The public and private sectors, by themselves, are imperfect. They cannot or are unwilling to meet all demands. Many argue (Elliott 1987, Fernandez 1987, Garilao 1987) that the voluntary sector may be better placed to articulate the needs of the poor people, to provide services and development in remote areas, to encourage the changes in attitudes and practices necessary to curtail discrimination, to identify and redress threats to the environment, and to nurture the productive capacity of the most vulnerable groups such as the disabled or the landless populations.

Achieving Millennium Development Goals through NGOs

During the past two decades, relevance of the role of voluntary sector has been in focus in India. In fact, the initiatives taken by the United Nations and its agencies in involving the voluntary sector for capacity building and contributing towards the speedier and less expensive processes of development has gained worldwide acceptance. As a consequence, the developed countries in particular and those which are still developing or are less developed have taken the idea of involving the voluntary sector responding to the complex processes of development at various levels. India has a large network of voluntary organizations working in the fields of Health, Education, Rural and Urban spheres. A large number of such organizations are making significant contributions in this direction in the State of Punjab.

With the objective of associating voluntary organizations in development and social welfare activities in an appropriate manner, the State Government is providing sizeable monetary assistance to such organizations to enable them to play a notable role in the development process. The target sectors for voluntary organizations are elementary and adult education; vocational training of adolescent girls and women from poor and needy families, Reproductive and Child Health Programme, animal care, National Health Programme, development of women and children in the rural areas and environmental improvement of urban slums and welfare of SCs/BCs etc. The emphasis is on encouraging self-employment through skill formation. Leading institutions in specific areas are suitably involved in providing gainful employment to the unemployed/under employed youth. While adopting the neglected segments of the society, the endeavor is to encourage community participation to the optimal extent both in planning and implementation with the help of mass-based self-reliant organizations and to take up projects to sustain the achievements already made. The aim of the Government is to reach the neediest in the society through innovation and experimentation of the NGOs.

In order to systematize the voluntary efforts in development, the State Government have issued policy guidelines in which special attention has been given to the idea of having a mother unit. The only mother NGO in Punjab at present is the 'Society for Service to Voluntary Agencies (SOSVA) (North)' for the Department of Health and Social Welfare. The funds are placed at the disposal of the concerned Administrative Departments which further release the same to the field NGOs through SOSVA(N). At present, the maximum Government support to an NGO in a single financial year for one project is Rs.10.00 lac per annum. The remaining amount, if required, is raised by the NGO concerned from its own sources and other local agencies. In no case, the grant to an NGO with more than one project should exceed Rs.15.00 lac in a single financial year. However, this condition does not apply to the projects under service sector, the nature of which is to create awareness among masses.

It is quite evident from the myriad of the activities carried out by the NGOs at a local level that their very purpose is welfare of the humanity, be it in any form. Exactly that is the aim of MDGs which were laid down by the UN. To support this view, the researchers put forth few characteristics that all the NGOs share in common irrespective of their area and scale of operations. They are:

1. Grass root approach: any NGO is more than welcomed amongst the general public, as they are not having profit motives at their core. This facilitates development of trust between the NGO and their beneficiaries.

2. Adaptation and Innovation: majority of the NGOs do not work on set patterns and systems. Their systems are dynamic and customized in nature. Also their basic aim being to serve humanity they are capable to undertake vast and varying nature of tasks in-line with their objectives.

3. Cost efficient and effective: They generally take charity and donations from the business houses, public and private funds, which makes them productive with almost negligible inputs. As they do not have profit motives, chances of internal corruption and frauds are less. Also people from the society itself are a part of these NGOs which are there due to the complaints from the existing system, hence they themselves act as watch-dogs making NGOs quite effective in their purpose.

4. Integrity and Sincerity of Purpose. At occasions NGOs are blamed to have secondary objectives of self-propagation. In certain cases it might be true, however, the basic purpose to serve humanity remains in-built to any NGO. People look towards them as their spokesperson, which possess resources, infrastructure and the courage to oppose any wrong doing by a public or private enterprise or individual. NGOs are looked upon as dedicated bodies for the cause, possessing sincerity and integrity by general public.

5. Expert management: NGOs are mostly well trained and possess the required skill set and expertise needed in their field of operation. Their man power and technical knowledge is up to date and they know who-and-where of the related field. Also they have mastered the art of measuring the effectiveness of their efforts. It is in the light of above characteristics and profile that NGOs seem to be appropriate instrument which can serve as a road to achieving Millennium Development Goals laid down by the UN in September 2000

Linking Partnership and collaboration

Road Map.....

After conducting this study, the researchers are of the opinion that there should be a slight shift in the paradigm to enable these NGOs work efficiently and effectively.

- Demands collaboration between government and non- governmental actors Calls for coordination at the national, intermediate and community levels requires a robust response to areas that have been neglected, such as child and maternal mortality, and strengthening comprehensive primary health care.
- The Ministry of Foreign Affairs bring to a public-private partnership and perform some activities like Raise awareness of what the private sector can do to help achieve the MDGs, Support cooperation with local authorities and local NGOs, Bring together private-sector parties and act as go-between, Help to replicate and scale up effective partnerships, Provide access to local networks and international platforms, Support local authorities' efforts to improve the local business climate, Provide funding (directly or through partners in the Ministry's network),Technology transfer, Innovation, Communication and marketing , Access to international and local value chains and markets, Product knowledge, services and expertise, Market-oriented approach, Financial resources
- For better development in MDG there is a great need of intervention of NGO for that more funds should provide to NGO to make formative research.
- While preparing policies and regulations at global and local level for MDG coordination of NGO could be motivated.
- Try to invest more money on NGO integrated approaches.

Conclusions

NGOs are the only organisations that truly care for the uncared for and those at the bottom of the social ladder. Ours is an encircling country that demands organisations that are passionate, devoted, and

dedicated to the country's progress. Thus, the government, leaders, funders, lawmakers, and the general public should support these organisations and assist them in resolving their grassroots concerns. Then and only then are their services unquestionably commendable in terms of rural poverty alleviation.

Countries will not achieve the MDG targets unless they place a greater emphasis on community-level interventions and strengthen the link between micro and macro levels. NGOs are well-positioned to play a significant role in scaling up community participation and interventions, as well as in connecting (Inform / Support) the micro and macro levels. There is an urgent need for NGOs to advocate for more integrated and equitable MDG targets.

In the context of the MDGs, Goal 8 lacks a precise target that adequately captures the several aims and activities required in the domain of global finance, including the issue of debt, capital flows, and a healthy system of development funding. As a result, more comprehensive targets should be set in this subject, as well as more and better indicators. Most critical, however, is the need to flesh out in greater detail and precision the many measures, policies, and frameworks necessary to transform the financial system into a critical component of a "global partnership for development," rather than the problem it is today.

We feel that we have been extremely effective in lobbying for and obtaining pro-poor laws, and as a result, India today has an excellent policy framework. We have sound legislation in place, including the National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme, the Right to Information, the Right to Education, and the Domestic Violence Act.

However, when one examines implementation on the ground, and particularly implementation from the perspective of India's most marginalised populations, one notices a significant disconnect between what is written and what is really given to impoverished people. Thus, that is the bridge, if you will, that we are attempting to fill, which is to enhance awareness of impoverished people's rights.

Thus, it is truly about information, organisation, and ultimately, demanding those rights, but doing so community by community requires a tremendous amount of effort. And if the government could be more proactive in disseminating information, as they are currently doing with the Right to Education - there is a massive effort on to educate the public about this law. If they were truly committed to, at the very least, raising awareness, that would be a positive thing.

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